

Evaluation of stability constants of consecutive ternary complex equilibria in aqueous and aqua-dioxan media

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Abstract : The stability constants of the mixed ligand complexes of L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (L-dopa) (L) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) (X) with Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} ions were determined pH-metrically at 303.0 K and an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L^{-1} (NaCl) in varying concentration of dioxan-water (0–60% v/v) mixtures. These studies establish the binding mode of the ambidentate L-dopa and phen in the ternary complexes. The trend in the variation of stability and concentrations of the ternary species with the dielectric constant of the medium was explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. The formation and distribution of different species with relative concentrations of metal and ligands, with varying pH were represented in the form of distribution diagrams. Influence of the solvent on the speciation was discussed based on the dielectric constant of the medium.

Keywords : Stability constant, dioxan, L-dopa, 1,10-phenanthroline, metal, species.

Introduction

Stability constants of metal complexes have been determined by different methods such as spectral method¹ and pH potential method². It is well-known that the simplest electro analytical technique for determination of stability constants is potentiometric method using the glass electrode. In recent years, considerable research has been carried out on modeling of mixed-ligand complexes in an effort to understand the nature of metal-ion complexation in biological systems^{3–6}. The ternary coordination plays an important role in biological processes and it occurs commonly in biological fluids, with several potential ligands, including certain amino acids, peptides and their analogues⁷.

The aim of the present work is to establish the stoichiometric compositions of the species formed in the 3,4-dihydroxy phenylalanine (dopa) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) with Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} ions in DOX-water mixtures. The structures of dopa and phen are shown in Fig. 1.

Results and discussion

Titration curves :

Different sets of titrations were performed with suc-

Fig. 1. Structure of the ligands.

cessive addition of ligand (X or L) and metal to the acid solution, using standard NaOH solution. Some of the titration curves are given in Fig. 2. These curves are the best evidences for formation of ternary species in the solution. Increased consumption of NaOH with the addition of metal ion infers the formation of the complexes.

Modeling of chemical speciation :

A preliminary investigation of alkalimetric titrations of mixtures containing different mole ratios of dopa and

Fig. 2. Alkalimetric titration curves of different combinations of the ingredients. FA = Free acid (HCl) titration; X = Acid + phen titration; L = Acid + dopa titration; MX = Acid + phen + metal (Ca^{II}) titration; ML = Acid + dopa + metal (Ca^{II}) titration; MLX = Acid + dopa + phen + metal (Ca^{II}) titration.

phen in the presence of mineral acid and inert electrolyte inferred that no condensed species were formed. The best fit models were chosen based on the statistical parameters⁸ like χ^2 , *R*-factor, skewness and kurtosis given in Table 1. A very low standard deviation (SD) in log values of overall stability constants (log β) indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of the deviations in the concentrations of the metal, ligands and the hydrogen ion at all the experimental points corrected for degrees of freedom) indicate that the models represent the experimental data. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for these systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of kurtosis and skewness should be three and zero, respectively. The kurtosis values in the present study of Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} indicate that some of the

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of dopa-M(II)-phen complexes (M = Ca, Mg and Zn) in DOX-water mixtures

% v/v	log β_{mlxh} (SD)					pH-range	NP	U_{corr}	χ^2	Skewness	Kurtosis	<i>R</i> -factor
	MLX	MLX ₂	ML ₂ X	MLXH	MLX ₂ H							
	Ca ^{II}											
0	12.96(14)	-	16.64(13)	20.54(12)	22.67(20)	4.0-9.0	39	1.0	23.38	-0.02	4.95	0.0062
10	11.76(9)	-	16.36(25)	21.27(25)	23.68(20)	4.0-9.5	37	6.4	6.22	0.60	4.23	0.0228
20	12.99(70)	-	17.40(44)	22.14(51)	24.08(83)	3.8-9.3	38	7.1	23.71	1.03	5.39	0.0229
30	12.88(71)	-	17.25(30)	22.42(23)	24.33(89)	3.0-10.0	66	17	25.76	-0.17	4.32	0.0265
40	12.34(21)	-	15.93(17)	21.31(28)	23.66(33)	3.9-10.0	49	4.4	13.87	0.66	4.03	0.0141
50	12.41(38)	-	15.91(30)	21.85(24)	24.46(30)	3.5-10.5	59	2.5	51.19	0.35	2.82	0.0304
60	12.38(25)	-	15.64(22)	22.10(16)	24.43(18)	3.5-10.5	65	1.1	24.06	-0.67	4.58	0.0217
	Mg ^{II}											
0	14.59(8)	17.48(66)	18.73(26)	23.53(13)	-	1.6-9.5	88	2.6	25.91	0.38	4.53	0.0088
10	14.32(14)	17.68(72)	18.81(50)	22.96(16)	-	1.80-9.8	92	2.5	19.89	1.19	7.28	0.0113
20	13.21(44)	16.15(68)	17.63(38)	21.93(19)	-	2.0-9.8	87	1.5	20.00	-0.73	3.65	0.0106
30	14.51(70)	16.89(56)	18.30(26)	23.91(15)	-	3.0-9.5	68	5.9	30.42	0.19	4.45	0.0175
40	14.25(8)	17.32(24)	18.29(33)	24.10(16)	-	2.0-10.0	99	3.1	88.12	-1.89	7.54	0.0255
50	13.18(35)	16.30(75)	17.41(20)	22.44(13)	-	3.5-9.5	63	5.2	37.78	2.21	21.12	0.0203
60	14.31(56)	16.73(18)	17.82(14)	22.90(7)	-	3.0-9.8	70	1.3	2.89	-0.03	2.74	0.0172
	Zn ^{II}											
0	15.91(29)	-	19.28(11)	25.67(7)	28.26(15)	1.6-10.0	152	8.1	180.76	1.36	13.02	0.0097
10	15.94(24)	-	18.22(25)	26.09(10)	28.14(31)	1.6-10.5	162	1.7	41.61	0.97	5.82	0.0062
20	17.11(23)	-	20.46(10)	26.98(6)	28.79(28)	1.6-10.5	127	5.4	38.83	0.95	6.78	0.0074
30	16.50(35)	-	19.99(16)	26.86(13)	29.39(19)	2.0-10.8	121	1.5	56.70	1.30	7.93	0.0093
40	17.46(27)	-	21.03(10)	27.73(6)	29.37(46)	1.6-10.8	142	2.6	53.57	1.14	9.49	0.0090
50	17.67(37)	-	21.73(18)	27.66(26)	29.70(66)	2.0-10.5	100	5.4	73.88	1.00	7.51	0.0108
60	17.62(19)	-	20.88(18)	26.91(11)	28.99(41)	2.0-10.5	120	4.0	49.13	0.55	4.88	0.0087

$U_{\text{corr}} = UI/(NP - m) \times 10^8$; NP = Number of points; m = number of constants; SD = standard deviation.

residuals are nearer to mesokurtic and others form leptokurtic patterns. The values of skewness recorded in Table 1 are between -1.89 and 2.21. These data indicates that the residuals form a part of normal distribution. Hence the least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic *R*-values recorded.

Effect of dielectric constant on the stability of ternary complexes :

The DOX-water mixtures are the combination of aprotic and protic solvents with a wide range of dielectric constant and with high solubility for polar as well as non-polar solutes. The increased basicity⁹ of DOX-water mixtures which is induced by co-solvent increases the stabilization of the protons. At the same time the coordinating solvent (DOX) competes with the ligands for coordination with the metal ions which decreases the stability of the complexes. Hence, the stability of the complex is expected to either increase or decrease.

The variation of overall stability constant values with co-solvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic. Born's¹⁰ classical treatment holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constants. The trends of the stability constant ($\log \beta$) values of the complexes of dopa with $1/D$ (D is the dielectric constant of the medium) of DOX-water mixture are given in Fig. 3. The trend is almost linear which indicates that either the dielectric constant or the long range interactions are responsible for the trend in stability. This linear increase in $\log \beta$ values indicates the dominance of the structure-forming nature of DOX over the complexing ability.

Stability of ternary complexes :

In the usual way with the help of the computer program MINQUAD75¹¹. To calculate the correction factor the computer program SCPHD¹² was used. During the refinement of ternary systems, the correction factor, protonation constants and binary formation constants of dopa and phen were fixed. The variation of stability constants with the dielectric constant of the medium was analyzed on the basis of electrostatic/non-electrostatic, solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions. The change in

Fig. 3. Variation of magnitude of stability constants ($\log \beta$) of ternary complexes of (A) Ca^{II} , (B) Mg^{II} and (C) Zn^{II} with dopa and phen with reciprocal of dielectric constant ($1/D$) of dioxan : (o) $\log \beta_{MLX}$, (◊) $\log \beta_{MLX_2}$, (◻) $\log \beta_{MLXH}$, (*) $\log \beta_{MLX_2H}$ and (Δ) $\log \beta_{ML_2X}$.

the stability of the ternary complexes as compared to their binary analogues was quantified based on the disproportionation constant ($\log X$) given by eq. (1) which corresponds to the equilibrium¹³⁻¹⁶ as shown (2).

$$\log K = 2 \log K_{MLX}^M - \log K_{ML_2}^M - \log K_{MX_2}^M \quad (1)$$

Under the equilibrium conditions one can expect the formation of 50% ternary complexes and 25% each of the binary complexes statistically and the value of log X shall be 0.6¹⁷. A value greater than this, accounts for the extra stability of MLX.

Another approach to quantify the stability of ternary complexes was based on the difference in stability ($\Delta \log K$) for the reactions ML with X and $M_{(aq)}$ with L and X^{14-18} , where L is the primary ligand (dopa) and X is the secondary ligand (phen). It is compared with that calculated purely on the statistical grounds as given in eq. (3).

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MLX}^M - \log K_{ML}^M - \log K_{MX}^M \quad (3)$$

The electrostatic theory of binary complex formation and statistical arguments suggest the availability of the additional coordination positions of the hydrated metal ion for the first ligand than for the second. Hence, the usual order of stability, $K_{ML}^M > K_{MLX}^M$ applies. This suggests that log K to be negative, although several exceptions have been found¹⁹.

The statistical values of log K for bidentate L and X are -0.4, -0.6 and between -0.9 and -0.3 for octahedral, square planar and distorted octahedral complexes, respectively. The negative values for log K can be understood that the secondary ligand forms a more stable complex with ML than the hydrated metal ion. Whenever the experimental values of log K exceed the statistical values, it can be inferred that the ternary complex is formed due to the interaction of ML with X or MX with L. log K values of ternary complexes are positive for O-donors (malonic acid, pyrocatechol etc.)¹⁴, negative for N-donors and intermediate or negative for amino acids with both N and O coordination sites^{20,21}. However, a very high negative value (-2.3) for Cu (ethylenediamine) (iminodiacetic acid) and a positive value (0.82) for Cu (phen)-(6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-sulphonate) was also observed.

The log X and $\Delta \log K$ values calculated from binary and ternary complexes and the equations for the calculation of $\Delta \log K$ and log X are given in Table 2. These values could not be calculated for some of the systems due to the absence of relevant binary species.

Table 2. Variation of stability of ternary complexes of dopa/phen in DOX-water mixtures

% v/v DOX	$\Delta \log K_{MLXH}$	$\Delta \log K_{MLX_2H}$	$\Delta \log K_{ML_2X}$	$\Delta \log K_{MLX}$	$\log X_{MLXH}$	$\log X_{MLX}$
			Ca ^{II}			
0	4.77	4.09	6.98	-	10.49	19.36
10	6.17	6.13	7.43	-	11.83	20.50
20	6.23	6.60	8.60	-	14.24	23.85
30	7.15	6.84	8.89	-	14.43	22.42
40	5.86	5.92	7.85	-	10.89	24.54
50	6.76	7.00	8.07	-	13.49	25.14
60	6.24	5.55	6.91	-	12.24	23.48
			Mg ^{II}			
0	8.44	-	9.23	-	10.85	8.50
10	7.74	-	9.59	-	10.99	8.23
20	5.87	-	7.87	-	14.11	10.91
30	8.74	-	9.09	-	12.11	9.70
40	7.20	-	7.79	-	15.42	13.57
50	7.39	-	8.61	-	13.49	12.24
60	7.24	-	8.42	-	12.17	12.73
			Zn ^{II}			
0	4.00	1.48	1.08	2.46	17.30	17.50
10	5.58	1.46	0.74	2.84	16.31	17.16
20	6.37	3.17	2.17	3.76	13.40	14.53

Table-2 (contd.)

30	6.28	2.89	2.60	3.63	17.44	17.62
40	6.90	4.71	3.51	4.59	16.39	16.01
50	6.61	3.43	3.85	4.62	15.39	16.09
60	6.18	2.97	3.67	3.68	14.23	16.30

$$\Delta \log K_{MLXH} = \log \beta_{MLXH} - \log \beta_{MLH} - \log \beta_{MX}$$

$$\Delta \log K_{MLX_2H} = \log \beta_{MLX_2H} - \log \beta_{MLH} - \log \beta_{MX_2}$$

$$\Delta \log K_{ML_2X} = \log \beta_{ML_2X} - \log \beta_{ML_2} - \log \beta_{MX}$$

$$\Delta \log K_{MLX} = \log \beta_{MLX} - \log \beta_{ML} - \log \beta_{MX}$$

$$\log X_{MLX} = 2 \log X_{MLX} - \log \beta_{ML_2} - \log \beta_{MX_2}$$

$$\log X_{MLXH} = 2 \log X_{MLXH} - \log \beta_{ML_2H_2} - \log \beta_{MX_2}$$

In the present study, the log X values range from 8.23 to 25.14 and these values found to be higher than those expected on the statistical bases (0.6). These higher values account for the extra stability of the ternary complexes, $\Delta \log K$ values are in the range from -0.74 to 9.59 which indicate that the ternary complexes formed by the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} were more stable compared to Cu^{II} . The reason for the extra stability of these complexes may be due to (i) the interactions outside the coordination sphere such as the formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands, (ii) charge neutralization, (iii) chelate effect and (iv) stacking interactions^{22,23}.

Effect of influential parameters on the stability constants :

Any variation in the parameters (the concentrations of ingredients) affects the magnitudes of equilibrium constants. Such parameters are called influential parameters. In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the concentrations of alkali, acid, ligands and metal ions. The results of typical samples given in Table 3 emphasise that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and acid affect the stability constant more than those of the ligands and metal ion.

Chemical speciation :

The distribution diagrams indicate the relative abundance of various forms of metal ions (chemical speciation) at different pH and dielectric conditions. A typical distribution diagram drawn using the formation constants of the best fit model is shown in Fig. 4 which contains

Table 3. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the stability constants of ternary complexes of dopa-Zn^{II}-phen in 60% v/v DOX-water mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β (SD)			
		MLX	MLXH	MLX ₂	ML ₂ X
Alkali	0	26.91(11)	20.88(18)	17.62(19)	28.99(41)
	-5	22.59(17)	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	22.30(19)	14.62(74)	12.55(16)	Rejected
	2	27.31(10)	23.03(15)	19.14(17)	30.52(15)
	5	27.61(18)	25.99(90)	21.22(32)	31.54(15)
Acid	-5	28.35(34)	26.60(33)	22.14(34)	32.47(24)
	-2	27.64(11)	23.19(16)	19.46(17)	30.85(15)
	2	22.31(17)	15.25(27)	12.63(14)	Rejected
	5	22.16(15)	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
	dopa	-5	26.26(16)	20.69(18)	17.04(20)
phen	-2	26.70(12)	20.85(18)	17.43(19)	28.83(41)
	2	27.08(11)	20.86(18)	17.77(18)	29.15(42)
	5	27.30(11)	20.77(19)	17.95(18)	29.39(41)
	-5	26.41(12)	20.21(15)	16.95(16)	Rejected
	-2	26.73(12)	20.64(17)	17.37(18)	28.59(58)
Metal	2	27.08(11)	21.13(18)	17.87(19)	29.39(32)
	5	27.31(12)	21.53(19)	18.25(20)	29.91(25)
	-5	27.18(11)	21.51(18)	18.15(19)	29.76(25)
	-2	27.02(11)	21.13(18)	17.83(19)	29.32(33)
	2	26.78(12)	20.64(17)	17.41(18)	28.65(57)
5	26.57(12)	20.30(17)	17.12(18)	28.12(99)	

protonated and unprotonated species like MLX, ML₂X, MLXH and MLX₂H. A stable ternary complex shall be responsible for metal ion transportation in bio-systems and the weak binary metal complexes make the essential metal ions bioavailable. The increased concentrations of complexing agents make the essential metal ions unavailable due to the formation of stable metal complexes.

The formation of the possible complex species can be

represented by the following equilibria.

Fig. 4 shows the formation of dopa-Ca^{II}-phen complexes in the pH range 4.0–10.0. At lower pH the species MLXH, MLX₂H and LH₂ form of dopa simultaneously increases with decreasing LH₃ and XH form of dopa and phen and free metal ion (Equilibria 4 and 6). As the pH increases the concentration of MLXH and LH₂ decreased and the concentration of MLX and ML₂X are increased (Equilibria 5, 9 and 10).

Fig. 4. Species distribution diagram of ternary complexes of dopa-Ca^{II}-phen in 40% DOX-water mixture.

Structures :

Depending upon the nature of the ligands and the metal ions, the structures of the ternary complexes are proposed in Fig. 5. Dopa and phen form strong bidentate complexes. Dopa at higher pH favors the (O, O) coordination. At physiological pH it is bound only through the amino acid side chain^{24–28}.

Fig. 5. Structures for the ternary complexes; S = solvent/water; M = Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} or Zn^{II}.

Experimental

Chemical agents and instrument :

0.05 mol L⁻¹ of L-dopa (Loba, India) and 1,10-phenanthroline monohydrate (Finar, India) are prepared in deionised triple-distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ concentration of hydrochloric acid to increase the solubility. 0.2 mol L⁻¹ stock hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) solution was prepared. 1,4 Dioxan (Finar, India) was used as received. 2 mol L⁻¹ sodium chloride (Qualigens, India) was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Concentration of sodium hydroxide solution was determined by potassium hydrogen phthalate and oxalic acid. In order to obtain clear inflection on the titration curve, the NaOH concentration at 0.4 mol L⁻¹ was preferred. 0.1 mol L⁻¹ solutions of calcium(II), magnesium(II) and zinc(II) chlorides were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (Merck, India) salts in triple distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ HCl to suppresses the hydrolysis of the metal salts. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification²⁹. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{30,31}.

Procedure :

For pH metric titrations ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter of readability 0.01 was used which was corrected before each measurement. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor^{32,33}. For the determination of stability constants of ternary species, the equilibration of the glass electrode was established by titrating strong acid against alkali at regular intervals. The calomel electrode was refilled with DOX-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. All the pH metric titrations were performed at 303.0 ± 0.1 K in media containing varying concentrations (0–60% v/v) of DOX-water mixtures. Titrations were carried out in the presence of different relative concentrations of the metal (M) to dopa (L) to phen (X) with 0.4 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. The details of experimental procedure and titration assembly are given elsewhere³⁴.

Conclusions :

The following conclusions have been drawn from the modeling studies the speciation of ternary complexes of Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} with dopa (L) and phen (X) DOX-water media :

(i) The ternary species detected are MLX, ML₂X, MLXH and MLX₂H for Ca^{II} and Zn^{II} and MLX, MLX₂, ML₂X and MLXH for Mg^{II}.

(ii) The values of $\Delta \log K$ indicate that the ternary species have extra stability compared to the corresponding binary species.

(iii) The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > dopa > phen > metal ion.

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